

TIPIK BO‘Z TUPROQLAR SHAROITIDA AFRIKA TARIQ‘I ORGANIK USULDA YETISHTIRISH AGROTEXNOLOGIYASI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada sug‘oriladigan tipik bo‘z tuproqlar sharoitida Afrika tarig‘ini yetishtirishda organik o‘g‘itlar qo‘llashining hosildorlikka tahsiri bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: tipik bo‘z tuproq, organik o‘g‘it, afrika tariq, hosildorlik.

KIRISH

Dunyo aholisi uchun yer – tabiiy resurslar ichida jamiyat uchun juda katta ahamiyatga hisoblanadi. Yurtimizda yer va tuproq resurslari eng asosiy tabiiy boyliklar hisoblanib, ulardan oqilona foydalanish va muhofaza qilish, umummilliy ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan ustuvor vazifalardan biridir. BMTning ma‘lumotlariga ko‘ra, hozirgi kunda dunyo bo‘yicha yiliga qariyb olti million gektar yer cho‘llanishga uchramoqda, haydaladigan yerlarning 40 foizdan ortig‘i irrigatsiya va melioratsiya ishlarida xato va kamchiliklarga yo‘l qo‘yilgani sababli degradatsiyaga uchrab, dehqonchilik, qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlari yetishtirish uchun mutloq yaroqsiz holga keltirilgan. Mamlakatimizda qishloq xo‘jalik ekinlaridan mo‘l va sifatli hosil olish maqsadida Afrika tarig‘ini respublika sharoitida ekish va uni organik o‘g‘itlash ishlarini amalga oshirish maqsadida Toshkent viloyatining sug‘oriladigan tipik bo‘z tuproqlari sharoitida tadqiqotlar olib borildi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI

Afrika tarig‘i hosildorligiga mineral o‘g‘itlar me‘yorini oshirib borish ham qo‘shimcha hosilning shakllanishiga ta‘sir etdi. Variantlar bo‘yicha qo‘shimcha hosil «HHVBC tall» va ICTP8203 navlarida 5,2-10,2 s/ga oralig‘ida tebranishi kuzatildi. Mineral o‘g‘itlar go‘ng bilan birgalikda qo‘llanilganda esa bu ko‘rsatkich 10,2 s/ga ko‘p qo‘shimcha hosil olinganligini ko‘rsatdi. Sug‘oriladigan tipik bo‘z tuproqlari

sharoitida 25 t/ga go'ng organik o'g'itlar afrika tarig'i donining hosildorligiga ta'sir etish bilan birga uning yashil massasiga ham ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatdi. Dala kuzatuvlarining ko'rsatishicha organik o'g'itlar afrika tarig'ining yashil massasining oshishiga ham ijobiy ta'sir etdi. 2021-2023 yilgi kuzatuvlarlar Afrika tarig'ining HHVBC tall navida o'rtacha yashil massa 389,5-453,5 s/ga ni tashkil etib, qo'shimcha hosil esa 64,5s/ga ni tashkil etdi. ICTP8203 navida ham xuddi shunday yaqin xolat kuzatildi.

1-rasm. Tajriba dalasidan olingan fotolavhalar

Toshkent viloyatining sug'oriladiagn tipik bo'z tuproqlar sharoitida Afrika tarig'i hosildorligiga va uning sifatiga organik o'g'itlarning ta'siri yuzasidan. Afrika tarig'ini tajriba dalalarida o'rganilgan navlari va oziqlantirish variantlari Toshkent viloyati sug'oriladigan tipik bo'z tuproqlari sharoitida chorvachilik sohasi uchun yuqori sifatli, to'yimli miqdorda ozuqa berishi, donidan ozuqa modda sifatida foydalanish mumkin.

XULOSA

Afrika tarig'ining 25 t/ga go'ng qo'llanilgan qo'llanilgan variantlarida don hosili HHVBC tall» va ICTP8203 navlarida yuqori natijalar olingan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI: (REFERENCES)

1. Баштова А.Б. Биологические особенности африканского проса. Бюллетень ботанического сада им. И.С.Косенко. Краснодар, 1997. – с. 65-67.
2. Башатова А.Б. Особенности развития и продуктивность растений африканского проса в условиях центральной зоны Краснодарского края. Дисс.канд.с-х.наук. – Краснодар, 1994
3. Белецкий С.М. Агротехника высоких урожаев африканского проса в степной зоне УССР. Автореферат дисс.канд.с/х.наук. –Харьков, 1959.16 с.
4. Jamoliddin Saporboy ugli. “Efficiency of application of herbicides which are samuray 33% ek, zellek super 10.4% ek and triflurex 48% ek against weeds in cotton fields” Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 2.09 (2021): 136-139.
5. Salakhiddinovich, Nasirov Bakhtiyor., Eshankulov Jamoliddin Saporboy ugli 2021 “Development of Irrigation Procedures for Shadow Varieties Planted After Autumn Wheat.” International conference on multidisciplinary research and innovative technologies. Vol. 1. 2021. [Google Scholar](#)
6. J Eshonkulov, B Kamilov Effect of irrigation regimes on the fertility of soybean and sunflower cultivars planted in repeated periods To cite this article: January 2023 IOP Conference Series Earth and Environmental ScienceDOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/1140/1/013006 [Google Scholar](#)
7. Norqulov U, Shamsiyev A, Eshonqulov J. Sardoba suv ombori toshqinidan keyingi tuproq tarkibidagi oziqa moddalarning o‘zgarishi// O‘zbekiston zamini//Ilmiy-amaliy va innovatsion jurnal–Toshkent №2-2023–B.71-74
8. Norkulov, U., Izbazarov, B., Tukhtashev, B., & Eshonkulov, J. (2022). Effects of Sardoba Reservoir Flood on Irrigated Land. International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology, 2(2), 40-42.
9. Norkulov, U., Tukhtashev, B., & Eshonkulov, J. (2022). Change of Mechanical Composition of Soils after Flood of Sardoba Water Reservoir. International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology, 2(2), 36-39.
10. Abdalova, G.N.; Eshonkulov, J.S.; Sulaymonov, S.O.; Abdullayeva, F.M. Improvement of Cotton Nutrition Procedure and Irrigation Technologies. ACADEMICIA Int. Multidiscip. Res. J. 2021, 11, 720–723. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Burievich, T. B., Olimovich, A. Eshankulov J.S., Turaevich, M.T 2021 Groundwater consumption and cotton productivity. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2(09), 130-135. [Google Scholar](#)
12. Norkulov U, Izbasarov B, Tukhtashev B, Eshonkulov J., Volume: 2 Issue: 2 2022 Effects of Sardoba Reservoir Flood on Irrigated Land, International Journal of

Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology e-ISSN: 2792-4025 40-42 p.

13. U Norqulov, Sh Axmurzayev, J Eshonqulov, S Raxmatullayev Toshkent viloyati sharoitidasoya dalasidagi zarpechakka qarshi zeta 100 g/l gerbitsidini qo 'llashning samaradorligi 2022/12/31 RESEARCH AND EDUCATION 503-507 [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]

14. Norkulov U, Tukhtashev B, Eshonkulov J., Volume: 2 Issue: 2 2022 Change of Mechanical Composition of Soils after Flood of Sardoba Water Reservoir, International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology e-ISSN: 2792-4025 36-39 p. [Google Scholar](#)

15. Ziyatov Musulman Panjiyevich, Shamsiyev Akmal Sadirdinovich, Kamilov Bakhtiyor Sultanovich, Abdalova Guliston Nuranovna, Abdurakhimov Shavkatjon Olimovich, Eshonkulov Jamoliddin Saporboy ugli. PJAEE, 17(6) 2020 Effective agrotechnology of cotton feeding in different irrigation methods. Palarch's Journal Of Archaeology Of Egypt/Egyptology 17(6). ISSN 1567-214x. 3415-3428 p. <http://www.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/1335> [Google Scholar](#)

16. Shamsiyev Akmal Sadirdinovich, Eshonkulov Jamoliddin Saporboyugli, Sultanov Umbetali Tazabayevich 2020 Growth and development of soy and sunflower varieties. Academician 10(11):1289-1291